

ISSUES OF EDUCATION IN THE MIDDLE AGES (IX-XII) CENTURIES AND DEVELOPMENT HISTORY.

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Annotation: This article talks about the development of educational issues in Central Asia. The great ideas of the Renaissance, especially in fine arts, are expressed in love of life, great trust in man, his will and mind.

Key words: Europe, renaissance, Central Asia, material, food, development, in Central Asia, the Somonites, the Karakhanids, the Kaljuks.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o`rta osiyoda tarbiya masalalarini rivojlantirish Uygʻonish davrining buyuk gʻoyalari, ayniqsa, tasviriy sanʼatda yorqin ifodalanganligi hayotga muhabbat, insonga, uning irodasi va aqliga katta ishonch bildirildilishi haqida soʻz yuritilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: yevropa, renessans, markaziy osiyo, moddiy, movarunnahr, taraqqiyot, oʻrta osiyoda, somoniyalar, qoraxoniylar, qaljuqiylar.

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о развитии вопросов образования в Средней Азии. Великие идеи Возрождения, особенно в изобразительном искусстве, выражаются в жизнелюбии, большом доверии к человеку, его воле и разуму.

Ключевые слова: Европа, Ренессанс, Центральная Азия, материал, современная еда, развитие, в Средней Азии - сомониты, караханиды, кальджуки.

It is clear from history that social development has not always been smooth. Along with the general development, mankind has experienced many obstacles, declines and hardships. After eliminating them, he restored his material and

cultural level and earnestly strived for new development. In science, such a large, significant rise is also called restoration, awakening, renaissance. In particular, such a renaissance occurred in Western Europe in the 15th-17th centuries after almost 700 years of superstition. The first renaissance period in Central Asia corresponds to the 9th-12th centuries and it took place under special conditions. The consequences of its scope and influence on the world civilization were fragmentary. The development of the extremely complicated political situation, social and economic changes that took place in Movarounnahr and Khorasan in the 9th-12th centuries had a strong impact on the country's cultural life. It is known that after Mowarunnahr was conquered and annexed to the caliphate, among other conquered countries, not only the religion of Islam, but also the Arabic language and its spelling were introduced in this country. Because Arabic was the state language of the caliphate. Also, in the Arab caliphate, the state language was also the language of science. In the 9th-12th centuries, when the Somanids, Karakhanids, Seljuks and Khorezmshahs ruled, there was relative peace, tranquility, harmony, closeness and solidarity among the people of Movarounnahr. As a result, the process of material production and cultural development in the country has accelerated. The life of cities improved, trade, handicrafts grew, population activity stabilized. Art, especially mural painting, had reached a new level. Sculpting, artistic woodcarving, carving, developed. The number of musicians and composers increased, there were family performances of flutists, dancers, and trumpeters. In these times, the mutual compromise of religious beliefs played an important role in the life of the population and the peace of the country. At the same time, the desire for natural sciences, understanding of the environment, and a wider knowledge of existence will increase. In particular, there is information that Sogdian calendars were compiled at that time, and there was an observatory in the area of the present Four Lakes. Therefore, the foundations of civilization and deep roots of material and spiritual culture have existed in Central

Asia since ancient times. The culture of our country, which was seriously damaged by the Arab invasion, recovered somewhat over the years, and science developed under new conditions, and significant positive changes took place in the cultural and educational spheres. By the beginning of the 9th century, the Arab caliphate also understood the importance of science and enlightenment better. "Baytul-hikma" ("House of the Wise") was established in Baghdad, the new capital of the caliphate in 832, and funds were allocated for its needs. Khazinat ulhikma", "dar ululum", the conversation of students and mentors continued, the reputation of the scientist was highly valued. The achievements of the Eastern Renaissance directly influenced the Renaissance in Western Europe. Because in the 12th-14th centuries, the contact between the Muslim world and the European countries increased. This process was particularly strong in neighboring border countries: Cordoba (Spain), the Caucasus, and the Balkan Peninsula. Europeans studied the works of Eastern scientists through translations into Latin, Spanish, Jewish languages or directly in Arabic. Ibn Sina's "Laws of Medicine", "AshShifa", Farabi's "Classification of Sciences", Ahmad Farghani's "The Complete Book of Celestial Movements and the Science of the Stars", Muhammad Musa Khorezmi's "Aljabr wal Altarba", Ibn Rushd, Abu Bakr Razi's works were translated and later published. done Algebra and algorithm sciences were formed thanks to Khorezmi's works. "The Laws of Medicine" served as a medical textbook in European countries for 7 centuries.

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